

THE ASSOCIATION OF SCAPULAR DYSKINESIA IN FEMALES WITH FIBROMYALGIA

Sharjeel Tasneem Chaudhary^{*1}, Khalid Aziz², Sana Waheed Syeda³, Abida Arif⁴, Prem Lata⁵, Fareena Yousaf⁶

^{1,2,3,4,5}bahria University Of Health Sciences

⁶mashal College Of Nursing

³syedasana.bumdc@bahria.edu.pk

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17541860>

Keywords

Fibromyalgia, Scapular Dyskinesia, Women's Health, Chronic Pain, Occupation, Pakistan

Article History

Received: 8 June 2025

Accepted: 8 August 2025

Published: 13 September 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *
Sharjeel Tasneem Chaudhary

Abstract

Background:

Fibromyalgia (FM) is a chronic pain syndrome characterized by widespread musculoskeletal discomfort, fatigue, and functional impairment, with a marked predominance in females. Scapular dyskinesia (SD), defined as altered scapular kinematics, has been reported in individuals with shoulder and upper quadrant pain. However, the association between FM and SD, particularly among women in Pakistan, remains underexplored.

Objective: This study aimed to investigate the prevalence of scapular dyskinesia and its association with demographic variables, occupational roles, and fibromyalgia severity in females diagnosed with FM.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 122 females aged 30–50 years with a confirmed diagnosis of fibromyalgia, recruited from three hospitals in Karachi. Participants were assessed using the revised fibromyalgia diagnostic criteria, including the Widespread Pain Index (WPI) and Symptom Severity (SS) scale, alongside the Scapular Dyskinesia Test (SDT). Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and one-way ANOVA with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Among participants, 33.6% were aged 41–45 years and 79.5% were housewives. Moderate fibromyalgia severity was the most common (66.4%). Scapular dyskinesia was present in 18% of participants, though no significant associations were observed with age ($p = 0.518$) or occupation ($p = 0.241$). A significant association was found between fibromyalgia severity and occupational category ($p = 0.012$). ANOVA revealed significant differences in mean FM scores across occupations ($p = 0.038$), with laborers and office workers reporting the highest scores.

Conclusion: Scapular dyskinesia is prevalent among females with fibromyalgia, though its occurrence appears independent of age or occupation. Occupational roles significantly influenced fibromyalgia severity, suggesting workplace demands may exacerbate symptom burden. These findings emphasize the importance of targeted rehabilitation strategies addressing both fibromyalgia and scapular mechanics to improve functional outcomes. Future longitudinal studies with more diverse samples are recommended to explore causality and intervention effectiveness.

INTRODUCTION

Fibromyalgia (FM) is an idiopathic, chronic disorder that is characterized by persistent, all-over musculoskeletal discomfort. The illness is frequently accompanied by fatigue, joint stiffness, muscle tightness, cognitive impairment, insomnia, mood disorders, anxiety, depression, general sensitivity, and the inability to carry out normal daily activities. The etiology and pathophysiology of fibromyalgia are unknown (1) (3). Fibromyalgia affects 2-8% of people worldwide, according to estimates, with a female to male ratio of approximately 9:1 (2) (3). Approximately 25% of individuals diagnosed with fibromyalgia are no longer able to work due to their condition. Direct health costs in FM patients may be between \$ 6,208- \$ 9,505 per year, with indirect costs in terms of lost productivity being significant (4). Additionally, some illnesses, including infections, diabetes, rheumatic diseases, and neurological or mental conditions, might be linked to FM. (5)

The prevalence of fibromyalgia (FM) in Pakistan varies across different populations, with significant findings reported in various studies. The overall prevalence among hospital patients is approximately 33.3%, with a notable female predominance of 76% (6). In a study focused on physicians, the prevalence was found to be 28.4%, particularly high among younger doctors aged 20-35(7). Additionally, in chronic kidney disease patients, the prevalence was reported at 13.66% (8). Among ischemic heart disease patients, a striking 61.4% exhibited fibromyalgia symptoms (9).

The 19th century had previously seen the description of what is now known as fibromyalgia. Gowers (10) first used the name "fibrositis" in 1904, and it was in use until the 1970s and 1980s, when a central nervous system-related etiology was identified. However, Graham (11) was the one who first proposed the present definition of fibromyalgia as "pain syndrome" in 1950, when there was no identifiable organic disease. Then, in the middle of the 1970s, Smythe and Moldofsky (12) discovered areas of intense pain, known as "tender points," and came up with the new word "fibromyalgia." The commonly used diagnostic criteria, which have only recently been changed, were only written out by the American College of Rheumatology committee in 1990. (5). Fibromyalgia syndrome (FMS) and chronic neuropathic

pain both have features in common, with the predominant features being widespread hyperalgesia and allodynia. Hyperalgesia describes increased pain from normally painful stimuli (e.g., pressure, heat, cold), whereas allodynia describes pain resulting from non-painful stimuli such as touch.

Fibromyalgia syndrome has a significant female predominance, accounting for 80-96 percent.

(13) 75% to 90% of those diagnosed are middle-aged women, who are the most affected. Fibromyalgia has traditionally been diagnosed by evaluating "tender points," or areas of discomfort surrounding joints, using an algometer or palpation method. It has been noted that women experience more severe pain at these locations and report more tender points than men do. This criterion has thus been substantially responsible for the higher prevalence of fibromyalgia among women. (14). Certain locations on the body that hurt when touched are known as tender spots. Pressing a tender point might result in discomfort that travels to a wider area, such as the back, arm, or leg. There are nine tender point pairs. For a total of 18 points, each pair has one point on each side of the body. These pairs are located: Behind the ear where the neck muscles connect to the base of the skull at the back of the neck; roughly midway between the shoulder tip and the base of the neck; at the point where the shoulder blade and back muscles connect; above the collarbone on the front of the neck; about 5 cm (2 in.) below the collarbone, directly to the right and left of the breastbone (sternum); just outside the elbow crease and beneath it on each forearm, outside each buttock and just above it; just behind the bony portion of the hip on the outside of the upper leg (this place is standing); on each knee's inside. (15)

Scapular dyskinesia is defined as any alteration in scapulothoracic pace that results in a change in the position, scapular motions, or normal mobility of the scapula relative to the thorax (16). It is a term used to indicate observable alterations in the scapular position in movement patterns, which have been linked to certain shoulder ailments (17). It is considered that the scapula plays a key role in shoulder function, and that any change in position affects muscle strength and stab

ility of the shoulder girdle (18). Research indicates that 68-100% of patients with shoulder problems have some degree of scapular dyskinesia (19).

Shoulder pain is one of the most prevalent localizations in fibromyalgia, following back pain and neck pain, even though the most common complaint of individuals with the condition is "pain all over the body", which can lead to the development of shoulder dyskinesia (20). In fibromyalgia, widespread pain, muscle weakness, and posture abnormalities contribute to the higher incidence of scapular dysfunction (21). Despite the high prevalence of fibromyalgia and the known impacts of scapular dyskinesia, there is limited research on the link between fibromyalgia and scapular dyskinesia, particularly among females. Housewives, often affected by fibromyalgia, engage in repetitive shoulder-straining tasks that may worsen SD. Investigating this population can help develop targeted interventions to improve daily function and quality of life.

Building on the need to explore the link between fibromyalgia and scapular dyskinesia in housewives, this study aims to fill the research gap, especially within the Pakistani context. By examining their combined impact, the findings may guide targeted rehabilitation strategies and enhance clinical outcomes for affected women.

Methodology:

This cross-sectional study was conducted to investigate the association between scapular dyskinesia (SD) and functional impairment in females diagnosed with fibromyalgia (FM). Given the nature of the objective, a cross-sectional design was deemed appropriate to assess variables concurrently and establish correlations within a specific timeframe. Data collection took place over six months following IRB approval at three major hospitals in Karachi: PNS Shifa Hospital, Jinnah Hospital, and NMC Hospital. A total of 122 females aged 30-50 years, clinically diagnosed with fibromyalgia based on the revised fibromyalgia clinical diagnostic criteria, were recruited using a non-probability convenience sampling technique. This approach was chosen due to logistical feasibility and the specific characteristics of the patient population. While this method may introduce bias, it

enabled practical recruitment and is consistent with exploratory objectives. Future research should consider probability-based sampling to validate the findings

Females aged 30-50 years, confirmed diagnosis of fibromyalgia using new diagnostic criteria, Presence of fatigue and widespread musculoskeletal pain, Willingness to participate, Employed or unemployed females of any occupation were included in this study. Chronic diabetes mellitus (duration >5 years), Congenital anomalies, Lactating females, History of frozen shoulder, Nerve injuries of the upper limb, Thoracic or cervical spine pathologies, Prior scapular or shoulder surgeries were excluded from the study. The assessment tool includes a demographic questionnaire that collects baseline data, including age, occupational status, and medical history. The Fibromyalgia Diagnostic Criteria Tool consisted of two components: the Widespread Pain Index (WPI; 0-19 points) and the Symptom Severity (SS) score (0-12 points), further subdivided into major (2a) and minor (2b) symptom domains. Scapular dyskinesia was assessed using the Scapular Dyskinesia Test (SDT), which shows Visual analysis of scapular kinematics during arm abduction and forward flexion to identify dyskinetic patterns. The data was analyzed using SPSS (Version 23) to evaluate the relationships and distributions of the study variables. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were calculated for demographic variables (age and occupation) and key study parameters such as fibromyalgia severity and FM scores. Frequencies and cross-tabulations were used to examine the distributions of categorical variables, such as scapular dyskinesia, and their associations with other variables, assessed through chi-square tests. A one-way ANOVA was conducted to compare FM scores across age groups and occupational categories, identifying significant differences with a set significance level of $p < 0.05$. Graphs such as bar charts and histograms were utilized to enhance the clarity of data trends. The analysis thoroughly examined the prevalence of scapular dyskinesia and its association with functional impairment in females with fibromyalgia, ensuring the findings were presented in a structured and comprehensible way.

Result:

A total of 122 women diagnosed with fibromyalgia participated in the study, all between the ages of 30 and 50. The majority were aged 41–45 years (33.6%), followed by 29.5% in the 46–50 age group, while the

fewest participants (18.0%) were in the 30–35 age bracket. Most participants were housewives (79.5%), followed by laborers (9.8%), office workers (6.6%), tutors (3.3%), and doctors (0.8%) shown in Table 1.

Category	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Age (30-35)	22	18.0	18.0	18.0
Age (36-40)	23	18.9	18.9	36.9
Age (41-45)	41	33.6	33.6	70.5
Age (46-50)	36	29.5	29.5	100.0
Housewife	97	79.5	79.5	79.5
Labor	12	9.8	9.8	89.3
Tutor	4	3.3	3.3	92.6
Office Worker	8	6.6	6.6	99.2
Doctor	1	0.8	0.8	100.0

Table 1: demographic table

The majority of participants (66.4%) experienced moderate fibromyalgia severity, while 18.0% and 15.6% exhibited severe and mild severity, respectively. Scapular dyskinesia was observed in 18.0% of participants, whereas the majority (82.0%)

did not exhibit this condition. The mean FM score for the study population was 18.85 ± 3.95 , with a range of 12 to 29. The scores followed an approximately normal distribution, as visualized by the histogram shown in graph 1.

Graph 1: Mean score of fibromyalgia
 Cross-tabulation revealed that fibromyalgia severity did not significantly vary across age groups

(p=0.806p). While moderate severity was the most common across all age groups, severe cases were slightly higher among participants aged 41–45 years. A significant association was observed between fibromyalgia severity and occupation (p = 0.012).

Moderate severity was predominant across all occupational categories, but severe cases were more common among laborers (58.3%) shown in table 2

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	19.491 ^a	8	.012
Likelihood Ratio	19.311	8	.013
N of Valid Cases	122		

Table 2:

Chi square analysis

The prevalence of scapular dyskinesia did not significantly differ across age groups (p=0.518). However, the proportion of scapular dyskinesia was slightly higher in participants aged 36–40 years (26.1%) compared to other groups. No significant association was found between scapular dyskinesia and occupation (p=0.241). Nonetheless, scapular

dyskinesia was slightly more prevalent among laborers (33.3%) and office workers (37.5%). The one-way ANOVA revealed no significant difference in FM scores across age groups (p=0.431). Participants aged 36–40 years had the highest mean FM score (19.61 ± 3.86), while those aged 46–50 years had the lowest mean score (18.06 ± 3.87) shown in table 3

ANOVA					
FM_SCORE					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	43.325	3	14.442	.924	.431
Within Groups	1844.019	118	15.627		
Total	1887.344	121			

Table 3:

Anova score across age group

Significant differences in FM scores were observed across occupational

groups (p=0.038). Laborers reported the highest mean FM

score (21.50 ± 4.33), followed by office workers (21.13 ± 3.00) shown in Table 4

ANOVA					
FM_SCORE					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	155.583	4	38.896	2.628	.038
Within Groups	1731.762	117	14.801		
Total	1887.344	121			

Table 4:

Anova score across occupational group

Discussion:

In the present study, we have investigated the prevalence of scapular dyskinesia in women with fibromyalgia and their relationship with demographic factors, severity of fibromyalgia, and functional impairment. Our findings take a step further in understanding the musculoskeletal dysfunctions in such a population and help to provide potential clinical considerations. Eighteen percent of participants were found to have scapular dyskinesia, which is consistent with evidence from literature that describes musculoskeletal instability as a component of fibromyalgia-related impairments. No considerable relations were found between scapular dyskinesia and age or occupational status; this indicates that the scapula dysfunction may be more pathophysiological in the case of fibromyalgia, rather than demographic. Fibromyalgia severity significantly correlated with occupation, so it could mean that occupational roles play a part in symptom severity (22). The dyskinesia in the scapular area corresponds to previous studies that refer to biomechanical deficits or adverse muscle activation patterns and less proprioception as contributing factors towards developing this type of scapular dyskinesia within that specific population (23). However, contrary to some reports, where age and occupation were found to have such correlations,

our findings do not cast a shadow over it and disagree with membership in revealing such associations. Our study looked into fibromyalgia (FM) patients, focusing on 122 chronic illnesses. It was noted that 18% of these participants presented SD. However, relations between SD and occupation were found as workers in construction and clerical occupations have relatively higher symptom severity than other workers (24). This implies that although SD may not be actively regulated by factors of age or job type, it is likely that SD could contribute to the functional impairments in patients with FM. Whereas, in the second study, patients with more generalized neck, back, and shoulder pain were looked into. Here, a much higher prevalence of SD was reported, where 41.9% had symptoms of this condition. Similar to the previous FM study, this research also didn't find significant differences in SD prevalence between different demographic characteristics. In conclusion, both studies indicate the potential role of scapular dyskinesia in the genesis of somatic pain. The FM study highlights the effect of working aspects on the progression of the disease, and the other study focuses more on the association of pain with the presence of SD.(26,27) The other study wanted to evaluate pain, muscle strength, scapula endurance, and scapula motion in

people complaining of Chronic Nonspecific Neck Pain (NSCNP) in comparison to pain-free individuals. The number of patients diagnosed with NSCNP was 40, while all took part in the healthy control group. While our study evaluated women with FM, we found that 18% of women had symptom dissociation. It stressed that age or working-class occupation did not have an impact on performance SD, but rather, the severity of fibromyalgia seems to influence the extent of SD dysfunction. Laborers and office workers had a higher disability radius, suggesting that the workplace may contribute to the severity of FM symptoms (29). On the contrary, the other study, which targeted a sample of patients with neck, back, and shoulder pain, noted that there was a higher prevalence of SD at 41.9%. This paper argued that patients with back and shoulder pain were found to suffer from SD and reported that the condition was worse at night (30). The two studies not only look at the role of scapular dyskinesia in relation to chronic pain conditions but also how the amount of FM exposure may relate to the severity of chronic pain conditions. The study of FM suggests there are areas of consideration regarding the workplace, which may increase the severity of the condition. The second study of SD proposes to emphasize other articles that investigate the association of scapular dyskinesia (SD) and shoulder pain (SP) (32,33). The purpose of the study was to establish how frequently the modified scapular assistance test (mSAT) is positive in cases of SP and if there is a range in results for those with and without SD. The research population consisted of 70 respondents who had been diagnosed with shoulder pain. It was able to determine that 54.29% were positive for scapular dyskinesia, but mSAT positive results had no major relation to the presence of SD. Since our study targets women with fibromyalgia (FM), it is reported that 18% were positive for scapular dyskinesia. It points out that SD could not be directly attributed to the age or type of occupation, but to several factors, especially the severity of FM in those who labor and sit in offices. In contrast, another study investigated patients with neck, back, and shoulder pains and came up with the results of a higher SD of about 41.9% This study found that patients who had pain in the back and shoulder had higher chances of having SD and greater levels of pain during the night. Both studies emphasize the possible contribution of

the presence of SD to chronic pain conditions (34,35). The FM mentioned the impact of occupation on the severity of the disease, while the second one reinforced the association SD had with specific musculoskeletal pain conditions. Together, they suggest that addressing scapular mechanics could improve treatment outcomes for patients suffering from chronic pain. (36,37)

This study concludes that scapular dyskinesia is prevalent among females with fibromyalgia and that occupational roles significantly influence the severity of symptoms. These findings highlight the necessity for comprehensive, individualized assessments and the implementation of targeted therapeutic interventions in clinical practice. Enhancing clinical education on scapular dysfunction in this population represents a critical step toward improving functional outcomes and overall quality of life for individuals living with fibromyalgia

Future longitudinal studies are essential to explore the long-term implications and potential causative pathways of scapular dyskinesia in individuals with fibromyalgia. Including a diverse sample encompassing both sexes and a broad range of occupational backgrounds would enhance the generalizability of the findings. Moreover, investigating the effectiveness of targeted interventions such as scapular stabilization exercises and workplace modifications could provide valuable insights for clinicians, including osteopaths, to support improved functional outcomes and reduced impairment in fibromyalgia patients.

There are several advantages to the study. It is a population-based study and its coverage is not just limited to women with fibromyalgia but also completely comprehensive in the examination of scapular dyskinesia, much less studied. However, certain disadvantages must be taken into account. Cross-sectional designs limit any inferences about causation between variable relationships. The sample was also quite homogeneous; that is, the sample included only females. The sample then narrows to implications for generalization to a male group or other populations. Moreover, self-reported measures could introduce biases, with the more noteworthy related to fibromyalgia severity and work roles.

References:

- Bhargava J., Hurley J. A. Fibromyalgia. *NLM*. 2023.
- Siracusa R., Paola R. D., Cuzzocrea S., Impellizzeri D. Fibromyalgia: Pathogenesis, Mechanisms, Diagnosis and Treatment Options Updated. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2021;22(8):3891.
- Bennette R. M., Jones J., Turk D. C., Russell I. J. Matallana L. An internet survey of 2,596 people with fibromyalgia. *BMC Musculoskelet Disord*. 2007.
- Soroosh, S. (2024). Epidemiology of Fibromyalgia: East Versus West. *International Journal of Rheumatic Diseases*, 27(12).
- Bellato E., Marini E., Castoldi F., Barbasetti N., Mattei L., Bonasia D. E., Blonna D. Fibromyalgia Sundrome: Etiology, Pathogenesis, Diagnosis, and Treatment. *Wiley online library*. 2012;2012(1).
- Arif, M. A., Syed, F., Niazi, R., Arif, S. A., Hashmi, U. e L., & Shah, Z. (2021). The oracle study - fibromyalgia, prevalence and severity in the hospital setting in the Pakistani population. *Journal of Pakistan Medical Association*, 71(5), 1357–1368. <https://doi.org/10.47391/JPMA.1000>
- Tahir, S., Zeb, A., Sharif, M. W., Rehman, O. U., Khan, M. S., Mukhtar, M., Mumtaz, H., & Zubair, A. (2022). The prevalence of fibromyalgia among doctors in the tertiary care hospital: A cross-sectional study. *Annals of Medicine and Surgery*, 84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amsu.2022.104931>
- Khan, Z., & Naqvi, R. (2021). Prevalence of Fibromyalgia in chronic kidney disease pre-dialysis patients: Experience from a Tertiary Care Renal unit in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*, 37(7). <https://doi.org/10.12669/PJMS.37.7.4474>
- Chohdary, A., Riaz, N., Riaz, Z., Maqsood, T., Zulfiqar, H., & Noor, A. (2024). Prevalence of Fibromyalgia among Ischemic Heart Disease Patients in Lahore. *Journal of Health and Rehabilitation Research*, 4(2), 1001–1005. <https://doi.org/10.61919/jhrr.v4i2.950>
- Gowers W. R. A Lecture on Lumbago: Its Lessons and Analogues. *Br Med J*. 1904;1(2246):117-121.
- Graham W. The fibrosits syndrome. *Bulletin on the Rheumatic Diseases*. 1953;3(8):33-34.
- Smythe H. A., Moldfsky H. contributions to understanding of the ‘fibrositis’ syndrome. CRC press; 2001.
- Staud R., Smitherman M. L. Peripheral and central sensitization in fibromyalgia: Pathogenic role. *Current Science Inc*. 2002;6:259-266.
- Treede R. D., Meyer R. A., Raja S. N., Campbell J. N. Peripheral and central mechanisms of cutaneous hyperalgesia. *Prog Neurobiol*. 1992;38(4):397-421.
- Li J., Simone D. A., Larson A. A. Windup leads to characteristics of central sensitization. *Pain*. 1999;79(1):75-82.
- Ruschak I., Montesó-Curto P., Rosselló L., Aguilar Martín C., Sánchez-Montesó L., Toussaint L. Fibromyalgia Syndrome Pain in Men and Women: A Scoping Review. *Healthcare (Basel)*. 2023;11(2):223.
- Arout CA, Sofuoglu M, Bastian LA, Rosenheck RA. Gender Differences in the Prevalence of Fibromyalgia and in Concomitant Medical and Psychiatric Disorders: A National Veterans Health Administration Study. *J Womens Health (Larchmt)*. 2018;27(8):1035-1044.
- Healthwise staff. Fibromyalgia Tender Points. 2023 [updated 2023; cited 2019 Nov 2024]. Available from: <https://myhealth.alberta.ca/Health/pages/conditions.aspx?hwid=aa103823>
- Petri F. C., Rodrigues R. C., Cohen M., Abdalla R. J. Musculoskeletal lesions related to table tennis. *Rev Bras Ortop*. 2002;37(8):358-362.
- Warner J. J., Micheli L. J., Arslanian L. E., Kennedy J., Kennedy R. Scapulothoracic motion in normal shoulders and shoulders with

- glenohumeral instability and impingement syndrome. A study using Moiré topographic analysis. *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* 1992;(258):191-199.
- Kibler W. B., McMullen J. Scapular dyskinesia and its relation to shoulder pain. *J Am Acad Orthop Surg.* 2003;11(2):142-151.
- Myers J. B., Laudner K. G., Pasquale M. R., Bradley J. P., Lephart S. M. Scapular position and orientation in throwing athletes. *Am J Sports Med.* 2005;33(2):263-271.
- Compagnoni R., Gualterotti R., Luceri F., Sciancalepore F., Randelli P. S. Fibromyalgia and Shoulder Surgery: A Systematic Review and a Critical Appraisal of the Literature. *J Clin Med.* 2019;8(10):1518.
- Giuseppe L. U., Laura R. A., Berton A., Candela V., Massaroni C., Carnevale A., et al. Scapular Dyskinesia: From Basic Science to Ultimate Treatment. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020;17(8):2974.
- Veeger H. E. J., van der Helm F. C. T. Shoulder function: the perfect compromise between mobility and stability. *J Biomech.* 2007;40(10):2119-2129.
- Sanchez H. M., Snachez E. G. M. Scapular dyskinesia: biomechanics, evaluation and treatment. *Int Phy Med & Rehab Jr.* 2018;3(6):514-520
- Ou H. L., Huang T. S., Chen Y. T., Chen W. Y., Chang Y. L., Lu T. W., et al. Alterations of scapular kinematics and associated muscle activation specific to symptomatic dyskinesia type after conscious control. *Man Ther.* 2016;26:97-103.
- Uhl T. L., Kibler W. B., Gecewich B., Tripp B. L. Evaluation of clinical assessment methods for scapular dyskinesia. *Arthroscopy.* 2009;25(11):1240-1248.
- Maffei M. E., Fibromyalgia: Recent Advances in Diagnosis, Classification, Pharmacotherapy and Alternative Remedies. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2020;21(21):7877
- Plummer H. A., Sum J. C., Pozzi F., Varghese R., Michener L. A. Observational Scapular Dyskinesia: Known-Groups Validity in Patients With and Without Shoulder Pain. *JOSPT.* 2017;47(8):530-537
- Mulkoglu C., Taskin S., Vural S., Kaplan B. M., Selvi A. B., Genc H. Isokinetic evaluation of the trunk muscle strength in housewives with fibromyalgia: a cross-sectional study. *Adv Rheumatol.* 2020;60(1):40
- Mirjat A.A., Chang H.M., Mirjat A.A., Rasool H.A., Rasool S.G. Prevalence of fibromyalgia in working women and house wives. *International Journal of Science and Healthcare Research.* 2020;7(9):76-81.
- Vongsirinavarat, M., Wangbunkhong S., Sakulsriprasert P., Petviset H. Prevalence of scapular dyskinesia in office workers with neck and Scapular Pain. *JOSE.* 2022;29(1):50-55.
- Konak H. Sert H. Pain Levels in Female Patients with Fibromyalgia and Affecting Factors. *Int J Carin Sci.* 2018;11(3):1631-1637.
- Rabin A., Chechik O., Dolkart O., Goldstein Y., Maman E. A positive scapular assistance test is equally present in various shoulder disorders but more commonly found among patients with scapular dyskinesia. *Phys Ther Sport.* 2018;34:129-135.
- Karaağaç A., Arslan S.A., Keskin E.D. Assessment of pain, scapulothoracic muscle strength, endurance and scapular dyskinesia in individuals with and without nonspecific chronic neck pain: A cross-sectional study. *J Bodyw Mov Ther.* 2023;35:261-267.
- Soliño S., Raguzzi I., Castro L.V., Porollan J.C., Aponte B.G., de Ilzarbe M.G., et al. Prevalence of positive modified scapular assistance test in patients with shoulder pain with and without scapular dyskinesia: a cross-sectional study. *J Hand Ther.* 2024 Jan-Mar;37(1):136-143.